

Qualitative Study on Dense-Labeling Model Generalization for Semantic Concept-Augmented Learning and Post-Hoc Analysis for Time Series Classification

Matilde Silva¹, André V. Carreiro^{1,2}, Leander Weber³, and Duarte Folgado^{1,2}

¹ Fraunhofer Portugal AICOS, Porto, Portugal
`matilde.silva@fraunhofer.pt`

² Comprehensive Health Research Center (CHRC), Porto, Portugal

³ Fraunhofer Heinrich Hertz Institute, Department of Artificial Intelligence, Berlin, Germany

For this analysis, we selected the first three samples of different classes to evaluate visible differences in the identified concepts (namely *rising*, *falling*, and *plateau*) and assess the behavior of the concept identification method. For datasets marked with (*), only a portion of the signal is shown, as the full signals would be difficult to perceive. Some datasets, such as ACSF1, were interpolated to higher resolutions (e.g., ACSF1: 14,600; Computers: 7,200; Earthquakes: 5,120 samples) to ensure precise concept alignment. Signals with lower variability and shorter lengths were resampled to the model’s input size, allowing reliable concept identification across most of the signal.

The dense-labeling model successfully identified concepts, sometimes at very fine granularity. For instance, representing noise as rises and falls rather than entire plateau segments. This fine-grained behavior can be influenced by interpolation: high interpolation of noisy segments may lead the model to interpret noise as rises and falls. However, datasets such as ACSF1 benefited from higher interpolation.

In segments with low variability but rapid local changes, or in signals with significant spikes (e.g., LargeKitchenAppliances, PigAirwayPressure), concept identification was less fine-grained, reflecting the inherent challenges posed by rapid changes. Such cases might have benefited from higher interpolation to better capture complete patterns.

Overall, this analysis confirms that the dense-labeling model effectively captures semantic concepts across diverse datasets while maintaining temporal precision.

